

Supplement 1. Search strategies

Sex-based differences in effectiveness of Immune checkpoint inhibitors in the treatment of advanced non-small-cell lung cancer: A systematic review and meta-analysis

Search strategies

Robust search strategies were conducted in PubMed, Embase (embase.com), Web of Science Core Collection, and Cochrane CENTRAL on 31 October 2023. An updated search was performed on 18 September 2024. See the next pages in this supplement for the full search strategies.

Methods for Developing the Search Strategies

An initial set of [11 key articles](#) was identified through a broad orientation of the literature. This process involved a combination of basic searches across multiple sources, reference checking, identification of similar articles, and a pilot search in PubMed. Keywords derived from these key articles were used to construct the initial search strategy for PubMed.

Following the development of the PubMed search strategy, it was rigorously tested and refined. Subsequently, the search strategies were translated and adapted for other databases.

Methods for Testing the Search Strategies

The same set of key articles was utilized to test and further refine the search strategies. One of the tests employed to evaluate the sensitivity of the search involved generating 'similar articles' and 'citing articles' for each key article. Articles from these generated sets that were not retrieved by the initial search strategy were screened for relevance. Relevant articles identified through this process were used to check for complementary MeSH and text words, which were added to the search strategy, if these terms added value.

Additionally, search blocks were tested by examining the articles retrieved using MeSH terms versus those retrieved using free text words in titles and abstracts. Relevant new text words identified through this process were incorporated into the search strategy.

The final search strategies were validated by ensuring that all key articles were retrieved across the databases PubMed, Embase and Web of Science.

Additional search methods

The references were screened of all articles selected for inclusion in the review, as well as the references of relevant review articles.

The following search in Google Scholar was conducted, of which the first 100 were screened for additional articles:

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nscle|"nonsmall cell lung"|"non small cell lung" pd1|pd-1|"immune checkpoint" "phase III"|"phase 3"|trial
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PubMed

("Carcinoma, Non-Small-Cell Lung"[Mesh] OR "nsccl"[tiab] OR (("non-small-cell"[tiab] OR "nonsmall-cell"[tiab] OR "nonsmallcell"[tiab]) AND ("lung"[tiab] OR "lungs"[tiab] OR "pulmonary"[tiab] OR "bronch*" [tiab]) AND ("cancer*" [tiab] OR "carcinoma*" [tiab] OR "neoplasm*" [tiab])))

AND

("Neoplasm Metastasis"[Mesh:NoExp] OR "stage IV*" [tiab] OR "stage III*" [tiab] OR "stageIV*" [tiab] OR "stageIII*" [tiab] OR "stage 4*" [tiab] OR "stage 3*" [tiab] OR "stage four" [tiab] OR "stage three" [tiab] OR "metasta*" [tiab] OR "advanced" [tiab] OR "M1" [tiab] OR "unresect*" [tiab] OR "nonoperab*" [tiab] OR "non-operab*" [tiab])

AND

("Immune Checkpoint Inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "atezolizumab" [Supplementary Concept] OR "avelumab" [Supplementary Concept] OR "cemiplimab" [Supplementary Concept] OR "durvalumab" [Supplementary Concept] OR "Nivolumab"[Mesh] OR "pembrolizumab" [Supplementary Concept] OR "sintilimab"[Supplementary Concept] OR "spartalizumab" [Supplementary Concept] OR "immune checkpoint*" [tiab] OR "checkpoint inhib*" [tiab] OR "pd1*" [tiab] OR "pd 1*" [tiab] OR "pd 1 1" [tiab] OR "pd1" [tiab] OR "pd 1" [tiab] OR "antipd1" [tiab] OR "antipd1" [tiab] OR "programmed death ligand 1" [tiab:~2] OR "programmed death protein 1" [tiab:~2] OR "programmed death 1" [tiab] OR "programmed cell death protein 1" [tiab] OR "programmed cell death 1" OR "atezolizumab" [tiab] OR "avelumab" [tiab] OR "cemiplimab" [tiab] OR "durvalumab" [tiab] OR "nivolumab" [tiab] OR "pembrolizumab" [tiab] OR "sintilimab" [tiab] OR "spartalizumab" [tiab])

AND

("Randomized Controlled Trial" [pt] OR "Clinical Trial, Phase III" [pt] OR "Clinical Trial, Phase IV" [pt] OR "Clinical Trial" [pt:NoExp] OR "Controlled Clinical Trial" [pt] OR "Clinical Trials as Topic"[Mesh] OR "trial" [tiab] OR (("phase 3" [tiab] OR "phase III" [tiab] OR "phase 4" [tiab] OR "phase IV" [tiab]) AND ("keynote*" [tiab] OR "study" [tiab] OR "studies" [tiab] OR "trials" [tiab])) OR "clinical study" [tiab] OR "controlled study" [tiab] OR "clinicaltrial*" [tiab] OR "random*" [tiab])

NOT

("Animals"[Mesh] NOT "Humans"[Mesh])

2,113 records 18-9-2024 (all key articles retrieved)

Embase (embase.com)

('non small cell lung cancer'/de OR 'nsccl' OR (('non-small-cell' OR 'nonsmall-cell' OR 'nonsmallcell') NEAR/2 ('lung' OR 'lungs' OR 'pulmonary' OR 'bronch*')) NEAR/2 ('cancer*' OR 'carcinoma*' OR 'neoplasm*')):ab,ti,kw)

AND

('advanced cancer'/exp OR 'lung metastasis'/exp OR 'metastasis'/de OR 'distant metastasis'/exp OR ('stage IV*' OR 'stage III*' OR 'stageIV*' OR 'stageIII*' OR 'stage 4*' OR 'stage 3*' OR 'stage four' OR 'stage three' OR 'metasta*' OR 'advanced' OR 'M1' OR 'unresect*' OR 'nonoperab*' OR 'non-operab*'):ab,ti,kw)

AND

('immune checkpoint inhibitor'/exp OR 'atezolizumab'/exp OR 'avelumab'/exp OR 'cemiplimab'/exp OR 'durvalumab'/exp OR 'nivolumab'/exp OR 'pembrolizumab'/exp OR 'sintilimab'/exp OR 'spartalizumab'/exp OR ('immune checkpoint*' OR 'checkpoint inhib*' OR 'pd1*' OR 'pd 11*' OR 'pd 1 1' OR 'pd1' OR 'pd 1' OR 'antipd1' OR 'antipd1' OR (programmed NEAR/2 death NEAR/2 ('ligand 1' OR 'protein 1')) OR 'programmed death 1' OR 'programmed cell death protein 1' OR 'programmed cell death 1' OR 'atezolizumab' OR 'avelumab' OR 'cemiplimab' OR 'durvalumab' OR 'nivolumab' OR 'pembrolizumab' OR 'sintilimab' OR 'spartalizumab'):ab,ti,kw)

AND

('randomized controlled trial'/exp OR 'phase 3 clinical trial'/exp OR 'phase 4 clinical trial'/exp OR 'clinical trial'/de OR 'controlled clinical trial'/de OR ('trial' OR (('phase 3' OR 'phase III' OR 'phase 4' OR 'phase IV') AND ('keynote*' OR 'study')) OR 'clinical study' OR 'controlled study' OR 'clinicaltrial*' OR 'random*'):ab,ti,kw)

NOT

((('animal'/exp NOT 'human'/exp) OR 'conference abstract'/it)

2,717 records 18-9-2024 (all key articles retrieved)

Web of Science Core Collection (Clarivate)

TS=("nscle" OR (("non-small-cell" OR "nonsmall-cell" OR "nonsmallcell") NEAR/2 ("lung" OR "lungs" OR "pulmonary" OR "bronch*") NEAR/2 ("cancer*" OR "carcinoma*" OR "neoplasm*")))

AND

TS=("stage IV*" OR "stage III*" OR "stageIV*" OR "stageIII*" OR "stage 4" OR "stage 3" OR "stage four" OR "stage three" OR "metasta*" OR "advanced" OR "M1" OR "unresect*" OR "nonoperab*" OR "non-operab*")

AND

TS=("immune checkpoint*" OR "checkpoint inhib*" OR "pd1*" OR "pd 1*" OR "pd 1 1" OR "pd1" OR "pd 1" OR "antipd1" OR "antipd1" OR "programmed death ligand 1" OR "programmed cell death protein 1" OR "programmed death 1" OR "programmed death protein 1" OR "atezolizumab" OR "avelumab" OR "cemiplimab" OR "durvalumab" OR "nivolumab" OR "pembrolizumab" OR "sintilimab" OR "spartalizumab")

AND

TS=("trial" OR "clinical study" OR (("phase 3" OR "phase III" OR "phase 4" OR "phase IV") AND ("study" OR "keynote"))) OR "controlled study" OR "clinicaltrial*" OR "random*")

NOT

DT="Meeting Abstract"

2,570 records 18-9-2024 (all key articles retrieved)

Cochrane Library (CENTRAL)

([mh "Carcinoma, Non-Small-Cell Lung"] OR nsclc:ti,ab,kw OR ((non-small-cell:ti,ab,kw OR nonsmall-cell:ti,ab,kw OR nonsmallcell:ti,ab,kw) AND (lung:ti,ab,kw OR lungs:ti,ab,kw OR pulmonary:ti,ab,kw OR bronch*:ti,ab,kw) AND (cancer*:ti,ab,kw OR carcinoma*:ti,ab,kw OR neoplasm*:ti,ab,kw)))

AND

([mh ^"Neoplasm Metastasis"] OR ("stage" NEXT IV*):ti,ab,kw OR ("stage" NEXT III*):ti,ab,kw OR stageIV*:ti,ab,kw OR stageIII*:ti,ab,kw OR ("stage" NEXT 4*):ti,ab,kw OR ("stage" NEXT 3*):ti,ab,kw OR "stage four":ti,ab,kw OR "stage three":ti,ab,kw OR metasta*:ti,ab,kw OR advanced:ti,ab,kw OR M1:ti,ab,kw OR unresect*:ti,ab,kw OR nonoperab*:ti,ab,kw OR non-operab*:ti,ab,kw)

AND

([mh "Immune Checkpoint Inhibitors"] OR [mh Nivolumab] OR ("immune" NEXT checkpoint*):ti,ab,kw OR ("checkpoint" NEXT inhib*):ti,ab,kw OR pdl1*:ti,ab,kw OR ("pd" NEXT I1*):ti,ab,kw OR "pd I 1":ti,ab,kw OR pd1:ti,ab,kw OR "pd 1":ti,ab,kw OR antipdl1:ti,ab,kw OR antipd1:ti,ab,kw OR "programmed death ligand 1":ti,ab,kw OR "programmed death protein 1":ti,ab,kw OR "programmed death 1":ti,ab,kw OR "programmed cell death protein 1":ti,ab,kw OR "programmed cell death 1" OR atezolizumab:ti,ab,kw OR avelumab:ti,ab,kw OR cemiplimab:ti,ab,kw OR durvalumab:ti,ab,kw OR nivolumab:ti,ab,kw OR pembrolizumab:ti,ab,kw OR sintilimab:ti,ab,kw OR spartalizumab:ti,ab,kw)

AND

((("phase 3":ti,ab OR "phase III":ti,ab OR "phase 4":ti,ab OR "phase IV":ti,ab OR phase3:ti,ab OR phaseIII:ti,ab OR phase4:ti,ab OR phaseIV:ti,ab) AND (keynote*:ti,ab OR study:ti,ab OR trial:ti,ab))

OR

((random*:ti OR "trial":ti) NOT ("phase 1":ti OR "phase I":ti OR "phase 2":ti OR "phase II":ti OR phase1:ti OR phaseI:ti OR phase2:ti OR phaseII:ti)))

1,413 trials